

Further Developing a Deterministic Neutron Diffusion Solver in PyTorch

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ABSTRACT

In our previous work, we demonstrated the potential performance benefits and feasibility of implementing finite-difference discretisations and linear solvers using convolutional operators found in the PyTorch deep learning library, when applied to solving the discretised multigroup neutron diffusion equation on structured Cartesian grids. At the same time, the methods we investigated had some significant drawbacks related to constraints on the uniformity of the grids on which they are employed, as well as the permitted discretisations of the diffusion operator, reducing their applicability to real use cases. This paper introduces methodological refinements to remove these constraints from our solver. We also detail some algorithmic improvements which are necessitated by the challenging, realistic, and large (both with respect to geometry as well as the number of degrees of freedom in the system) test problem, without which our solver can sometimes be numerically unstable. The test problem is a detailed, non-uniformly-spaced, pin-by-pin, quarter-core model with high aspect ratios, derived from the Nuclear Energy Agency (NEA) Tennessee Valley Authority (TVA) Watts Bar Unit 1 Multi-Physics benchmark. We show that, when accelerated by a GPU, our solver is capable of computing a flux solution converged to the same tolerances almost two orders of magnitude faster than a well-verified and validated single-CPU counterpart written in a compiled language. It does so conveniently, harnessing GPU acceleration without ever having to dip out of using high-level operations in the PyTorch library during programming, further demonstrating the practical advantages of the NN4PDEs methodology.

Keywords: neutron diffusion equation, convolution, numerical discretisation, GPU, reactor physics

1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of hardware such as GPUs, as well as software frameworks and libraries such as PyTorch [1], have been driven by recent advances in artificial intelligence. Originally intended for deep learning applications, these frameworks also provide a general-purpose computational capability. For instance, PyTorch (which is used in this work, but this could equally be *any* high-level AI library implementing similar operations), offers mature GPU support and device-agnostic code abstractions, which greatly reduce the lower-level implementation burden often associated with such architectures. This makes PyTorch particularly appealing for use in implementing deterministic solvers, allowing for rapid prototyping and experimentation while remaining performant on GPUs and not requiring explicit familiarity with device-specific APIs. The backpropagation algorithm inherent to PyTorch tensors allows for automatic differentiation, and therefore sensitivity evaluation, facilitating use in data assimilation and uncertainty quantification workflows. Solvers can also be combined with trained AI components, supporting hybrid modelling approaches which combine deterministic physics with learned behaviour. The NN4PDEs methodology [2] uses convolutional operators — a common deep learning primitive — to solve partial differential equations deterministically, with kernels that are not learned but instead

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uniquely determined by the chosen discretisation. This work directly builds on our previous work which utilised this approach applied to the neutron diffusion equation on structured axis-wise uniform Cartesian grids [3]. There, we showed the methodology has computational and implementation advantages, but also inherent limitations. Here, we introduce the formulation of a spatially-varying convolutional operator, which allows the grid to be non-uniformly-spaced and permits more tailored discretisations, while outlining how performance in its computation is maintained. We use a challenging test problem to quantify the benefits of this approach and evaluate our methodological refinements, while detailing some other solver developments this required. Results are compared versus the diffusion solver module in WIMS[®] [4], which is part of the ANSWERS[®] Software Package: its most recent version, WIMS11B.RU0, was released in 2022.

2. METHODOLOGY

Here, we define the equation that is to be solved and outline the challenges in its implementation using convolutional operators.

2.1. Problem Definition

One form of the multigroup neutron diffusion equation, when discretised using the cell-centered finite-difference method on a non-uniform structured Cartesian grid, may be written:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{-4D_{i,j,k,g}D_{i-1,j,k,g}}{\Delta x_i(\Delta x_i + \Delta x_{i-1})(D_{i,j,k,g} + D_{i-1,j,k,g})} \phi_{i-1,j,k,g} + \frac{-4D_{i,j,k,g}D_{i+1,j,k,g}}{\Delta x_i(\Delta x_i + \Delta x_{i+1})(D_{i,j,k,g} + D_{i+1,j,k,g})} \phi_{i+1,j,k,g} + \\
 & \frac{-4D_{i,j,k,g}D_{i,j-1,k,g}}{\Delta y_i(\Delta y_i + \Delta y_{j-1})(D_{i,j,k,g} + D_{i,j-1,k,g})} \phi_{i,j-1,k,g} + \frac{-4D_{i,j,k,g}D_{i,j+1,k,g}}{\Delta y_i(\Delta y_i + \Delta y_{j+1})(D_{i,j,k,g} + D_{i,j+1,k,g})} \phi_{i,j+1,k,g} + \\
 & \frac{-4D_{i,j,k,g}D_{i,j,k-1,g}}{\Delta z_i(\Delta z_i + \Delta z_{k-1})(D_{i,j,k,g} + D_{i,j,k-1,g})} \phi_{i,j,k-1,g} + \frac{-4D_{i,j,k,g}D_{i,j,k+1,g}}{\Delta z_i(\Delta z_i + \Delta z_{k+1})(D_{i,j,k,g} + D_{i,j,k+1,g})} \phi_{i,j,k+1,g} + \\
 & \left(\sum_{(p,q,r) \in \{(\pm 1,0,0), (0,\pm 1,0), (0,0,\pm 1)\}} \frac{-4D_{i,j,k,g}D_{i+p,j+q,k+r,g}}{\Delta_{i,j,k,p,q,r}(D_{i,j,k,g} + D_{i+p,j+q,k+r,g})} \right) \phi_{i,j,k,g} + \Sigma_g^R \phi_{i,j,k,g} \\
 & = \sum_{g' \neq g}^G \Sigma_{i,j,k,g,g'}^s \phi_{i,j,k,g'} + \frac{\chi_g}{k_{\text{eff}}} \sum_{g'=1}^G \nu_{i,j,k,g'} \Sigma_{i,j,k,g'}^f \phi_{i,j,k,g'} = Q_{i,j,k,g}, \forall g \in \{1, \dots, G\}, \forall (i, j, k) \in \mathcal{M}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

The notation is standard. \mathcal{M} defines the set of all cell indices in the grid, D the diffusion coefficient, ϕ the scalar flux, Σ^R the macroscopic removal cross-section, Σ^s the scatter cross-section, Σ^f the fission cross-section, ν the mean number of neutrons produced per fission and k_{eff} the effective multiplication factor. The subscripts i, j, k refer to cell indices, whereas subscripts g, g' refer to energy groups to which a given quantity belongs. $\Delta_{i,j,k,p,q,r} := |p|\Delta x_i(\Delta x_i + \Delta x_{i+p}) + |q|\Delta y_j(\Delta y_j + \Delta y_{j+q}) + |r|\Delta z_k(\Delta z_k + \Delta z_{k+r})$, is a helper function to simplify notation.

(1) can be written more concisely as a generalised eigenvalue problem,

$$A\phi = \lambda B\phi, \tag{2}$$

where $\lambda = \frac{1}{k_{\text{eff}}}$ and A is a seven-stripe matrix.

If, and only if, the cell spacings are assumed to be axis-wise uniform, and the harmonic means of diffusion coefficients are replaced by their arithmetic means, then (1) may be solved by a multigrid method

[3] implemented entirely using operations found in the PyTorch library. These limitations arise from the constraints on discrete convolutions, which are used to apply the finite-difference stencil, and to multiply and sum terms corresponding to off-diagonal elements of the A -matrix within the solver.

2.2. Spatially-varying Convolutions

The implementation of standard convolutional operators typically only permits the specification of one kernel (stencil) over the whole grid, and to allow for non-uniform spacing, we require a unique stencil for each computational cell. The output y of a standard convolution, say f , with kernel w on a grid x can in general be written:

$$y_{i,j,k} = f(x;w)_{i,j,k} = \sum_{p=-l}^l \sum_{q=-l}^l \sum_{r=-l}^l w^{p,q,r} x_{i+p,j+q,k+r}, \quad (3)$$

where, for example, for a three-by-three kernel, $l = 1$. We generalise this slightly and allow w to vary for each cell in the output, i.e., now,

$$y_{i,j,k} = F(x;w)_{i,j,k} = \sum_{p=-l}^l \sum_{q=-l}^l \sum_{r=-l}^l w_{i,j,k}^{p,q,r} x_{i+p,j+q,k+r}, \quad (4)$$

where we define the operator F to be a *spatially-varying convolution*.

2.3. Computing Spatially-varying Convolutions

Though spatially-varying convolutions are not typically implemented in libraries, we may do so ourselves by composing existing PyTorch operations to keep our implementation as efficient as possible. We adapt a common approach known as the "im2col", "direct" or "explicit GEMM" algorithm for standard convolutions to our case where the kernel is allowed to vary by cell.

A visual representation of our algorithm on a sample 3-by-3 input grid and 2-by-2 kernel (unique for each output cell) can be seen in Figure 1. We use the colour green to indicate the input values and operations from which a particular output cell was derived. The local convolutional, stencil-like operations are mapped to dense matrix-matrix multiplication, which allows us to exploit GEMM kernels, which are already highly-optimised. To minimise redundant computation and memory usage, the GEMM step is instead condensed to a long dot product and subsequent grouped summation and reshaping, between the flattened weight matrix and flattened im2col matrix.

2.4. Solving the Equation

Equation (2) is solved using a traditional outer-inner solution procedure, where power iterations are alternated with linear system solutions to converge on k_{eff} and ϕ .

With the spatially-varying convolution in hand, we may now write down an operator, $F_s(\cdot, w^{\text{diff}})$, whose action multiplies and sums all terms corresponding to off-diagonal entries of the A -matrix in (1). Its associated kernel w^{diff} is a tensor (in the PyTorch sense) of size $[G, N_x, N_y, N_z, 3, 3, 3]$ (where N_x, N_y, N_z represent the number of computational cells in the grid in the direction of each coordinate axis) defined by the following:

Figure 1. A visual summary of the *im2col*-like algorithm applied to computing a spatially-varying convolution.

$$\begin{aligned}
 (w^{\text{diff}})_{g,i,j,k,p,q,1} &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{-4D_{i,j,k,g}D_{i,j,k-1,g}}{\Delta z_i(\Delta z_i + \Delta z_{k-1})(D_{i,j,k,g} + D_{i,j,k-1,g})} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \\
 (w^{\text{diff}})_{g,i,j,k,p,q,2} &= \\
 \left[\begin{array}{ccc} 0 & \frac{-4D_{i,j,k,g}D_{i,j+1,k,g}}{\Delta y_i(\Delta y_i + \Delta y_{j+1})(D_{i,j,k,g} + D_{i,j+1,k,g})} & 0 \\ \frac{-4D_{i,j,k,g}D_{i-1,j,k,g}}{\Delta x_i(\Delta x_i + \Delta x_{i-1})(D_{i,j,k,g} + D_{i-1,j,k,g})} & 0 & \frac{-4D_{i,j,k,g}D_{i+1,j,k,g}}{\Delta x_i(\Delta x_i + \Delta x_{i+1})(D_{i,j,k,g} + D_{i+1,j,k,g})} \\ 0 & \frac{-4D_{i,j,k,g}D_{i,j-1,k,g}}{\Delta y_i(\Delta y_i + \Delta y_{j-1})(D_{i,j,k,g} + D_{i,j-1,k,g})} & 0 \end{array} \right], \quad (5) \\
 (w^{\text{diff}})_{g,i,j,k,p,q,3} &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{-4D_{i,j,k,g}D_{i,j,k+1,g}}{\Delta z_i(\Delta z_i + \Delta z_{k+1})(D_{i,j,k,g} + D_{i,j,k+1,g})} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \\
 \forall g \in \{1, \dots, G\}, \forall (i, j, k) \in \mathcal{M}, \forall p, q = 1, 2, 3.
 \end{aligned}$$

It follows that we can write down an operator, $J(\boldsymbol{\phi}^{(n)})$, that performs one Jacobi iteration within each within-group linear system defined by (2):

$$\boldsymbol{\phi}^{(n+1)} = J(\boldsymbol{\phi}^{(n)}) = (\mathbf{A}^{\text{diag}})^{\odot -1} (\mathbf{Q} - F_s(\boldsymbol{\phi}^{(n)}; w^{\text{diff}})). \quad (6)$$

Therefore, we can also calculate the residual $\mathbf{r}^{(n)}$ of the current solution $\boldsymbol{\phi}^{(n)}$ from:

$$\mathbf{r}^{(n)} = \mathbf{Q} - (\mathbf{A}^{\text{diag}} \odot \boldsymbol{\phi}^{(n)} + F_s(\boldsymbol{\phi}^{(n)}; w^{\text{diff}})), \quad (7)$$

where A^{diag} represents the strictly diagonal coefficients of the A -matrix, \odot defines a Hadamard (point-wise) product and a superscript of \odot^{-1} its inverse, and bold-faced symbols are now understood to represent tensors storing the relevant quantities within each computational cell in the grid and energy group. This allows us to implement a V-cycle multigrid method for solving (2) using the same formulation as in [3]. The only difference in our implementation here is that we add a number of explicit pre- and post-smoothing iterations.

In implementing the functionality for non-uniform finite-differencing in this way, we lose the ability to call highly-optimised cuDNN [5] kernels for the standard convolution (which PyTorch may do under the hood), which may result in a performance loss. At the same time, we go from requiring two convolutions to compute the action of J to just one compared to the formulation in [3]. It is the hope that this, combined with the PyTorch JIT graph compilation functionality, may overcome some of that performance loss.

2.5. Algorithmic Developments to the Solver

It was found that, even with the new harmonic mean discretisation, the solver was not numerically stable when applied to the test problem, unless a very high number of smoothing iterations were used, which significantly decreased its computational performance. Therefore, in addition to the remarks in the previous sections about smoothing and harmonic means, to improve robustness, a series of other algorithmic changes were also made to the solver.

2.5.1. Cell-volume corrections

A method of correcting residuals and correction terms during the restriction and interpolation operations within the multigrid has been implemented. It is hypothesised that this may be useful to decrease instabilities caused by large ratios between the spacings of neighbouring cells (which may be aggregated during grid coarsening). If \mathcal{M} denotes a fine grid and \mathcal{N} its corresponding coarsened grid, then we can include cell-volume corrections in the restriction and interpolation between these two grids rather than assigning uniform weights to cells which are aggregated. The volume-weighted restricted residual can then be given by:

$$r_{i,j,k}^{\mathcal{N}} = \frac{\sum_{c \in C(i,j,k)} V_c^{\mathcal{M}} r_c^{\mathcal{M}}}{\sum_{c \in C(i,j,k)} V_c^{\mathcal{M}}} = \left(\frac{S(\mathbf{V}^{\mathcal{M}} \odot \mathbf{r}^{\mathcal{M}})}{S(\mathbf{V}^{\mathcal{M}})} \right)_{i,j,k}, \quad (8)$$

where $C(i, j, k)$ denotes the set of fine cells which aggregate into coarse cell (i, j, k) , and V is used to denote cell volumes. This can be readily implemented by composing pointwise multiplies with a *standard* convolution with stride 2 and $2 \times 2 \times 2$ unit kernel, denoted S , for the numerator and the same convolution applied to only the cell volumes for the denominator.

Similarly, when interpolating the solution correction term e , from \mathcal{N} to \mathcal{M} , we can scale it by a volume correction term:

$$e_{i,j,k}^{\mathcal{M}} = k_{i,j,k} \tilde{e}_{i,j,k} = \frac{V_{i,j,k}^{\mathcal{M}}}{\tilde{V}_{i,j,k}^{\mathcal{M}}} \tilde{e}_{i,j,k} = \left(\frac{\mathbf{V}^{\mathcal{N}}}{U(\mathbf{V}^{\mathcal{N}})} \odot U(\mathbf{e}^{\mathcal{N}}) \right)_{i,j,k}, \quad (9)$$

where tildes denote interpolated quantities; $U(\cdot)$ is an Upsample layer with trilinear interpolation, available natively in PyTorch. The denominator in (8) and the correction factors in (9) can be computed once for each multigrid level and cached.

2.5.2. Damped Jacobi smoother

A comparatively straightforward development, but one that greatly influenced the convergence behaviour of the solver on the test problem, is modifying the Jacobi smoother (6) to allow for a relaxation parameter ω , which is standard in multigrid method theory. This slightly alters J to be:

$$\phi^{(n+1)} = J_{\omega}(\phi^{(n)}) = \omega(A^{\text{diag}})^{\odot -1}(\mathbf{Q} - F_s(\phi^{(n)}; w^{\text{diff}})) + (1 - \omega)\phi^{(n)}. \quad (10)$$

Typically, $\omega \leq 1$. A value that works well on the test problem is given in Section 3.2.

3. TEST MODEL AND PERFORMANCE COMPARISONS

In this section, we look at some solve time comparisons between the PyTorch-written multigrid solver, and the WIMS diffusion solver module, MERLIN [4]. The test model is a reactor quarter-core derived from the NEA TVA Watts Bar Unit 1 Multi-Physics benchmark, Exercise 1 [6]. Gaps and end plugs in fuel, pyrex and control rods are omitted; thimble plugs are omitted. The core barrel is modelled explicitly; the core baffle is modelled semi-explicitly; the neutron pads are modelled implicitly; the core vessel is not modelled.

The test problem is a diffusion flux solve on a homogenised pin-by-pin (with a 2×2 mesh within each pin-cell) representation of this model with non-uniform spacing along all axes. Fuel assembly grids are modelled explicitly, which contributes to the irregularity of the spatial mesh. There are 30 axial planes in our model, meaning there is a total of 2.7 million computational cells in the spatial domain. Many regions in the problem have high aspect ratios and spacing ratios between adjacent cells. It is these two characteristics that prompted the development described in Section 2.5.1. We choose to discretise the energy range into two energy groups.

3.1. Test Environment

All tests are performed on the same machine. This is comprised of an AMD EPYC 9354 32-core CPU and an NVIDIA L40S GPU with 48 GB of VRAM. Timings provided in tables are the mean of a number of runs of each solver.

3.2. Solve Times

Timings for a number of different solver configurations are provided; different floating point precision models are also tested for the PyTorch solver, given it uses a GPU marketed towards generative AI and graphics, where single-precision (or even less) is typically considered to be sufficient.

In all cases for both solvers, the solutions are converged to the same tolerances in the outer iteration: a maximum relative change in the flux of 1.0×10^{-4} , a tolerance in the flux change relative L_2 -norm of 1.0×10^{-5} and a tolerance in the relative change in k_{eff} of 1.0×10^{-6} . For the inner linear systems, MERLIN uses a group sweep preconditioned conjugate gradient method, and converges these solutions to a tolerance of 1.0×10^{-6} . The PyTorch Multigrid solver performs a single V-cycle per outer iteration rather than iterating to a tolerance, and does so for both energy groups in parallel (rather than solving for each group in series and resolving the scatter source in-between, like MERLIN). For both solvers, only fission regions contribute to the convergence checks on the flux in the outer iteration.

A Chebyshev polynomial acceleration method was also implemented within the PyTorch solver, which we use to accelerate the scalar flux in the outer iteration (another common choice is to accelerate the fission source instead). This is identical to the method employed by MERLIN. Toggling this on or off was not found to significantly impact the stability of the solution within the PyTorch solver; only the rate of its convergence.

The PyTorch multigrid solver has a number of parameters which can be tuned to the problem. One combination that we have empirically found by grid search to work well for this particular test problem is:

- 4 multigrid levels,
- 5 weighted Jacobi smoothing iterations on all levels but the coarsest, including pre- and post-smoothing, which tapers off to 2 as the outer iteration converges,
- a Jacobi relaxation parameter $\omega = 0.9$,
- 15 weighted Jacobi iterations on the coarsest level, which also tapers off to just 2.

Table I below shows the flux solve times for the test problem and Figure 2 shows a sample of the results. Matrix / kernel assembly or runtime JIT compile times are not included in the solve time. The total JIT compile time was around 4s, but it should be noted that JIT-compiled functions are cached by PyTorch, and need only be compiled once per flux grid size (e.g. in the context of a coupled calculation, or one for multiple configurations).

Table I. Performance metrics for the test problem.

Solver	Final k_{eff}	Solve time	Rel. solve speed	Outer iterations	Inner iterations	FP model
MERLIN	0.99527	255.95s	1.00	90	3831	FP64
PyTorch	0.99549	7.84s	32.65	195	11416	FP64
PyTorch	0.99548	3.55s	72.10	199	10346	FP32

Figure 2. Left: the geometry of the test problem. Middle: the scalar flux in energy group 1. Right: the scalar flux in energy group 2. Maps are taken through a particular axial slice in the active region, as given by the FP32 PyTorch solver.

The PyTorch solver is significantly faster than the single-CPU MERLIN counterpart, with speed-up factors approaching two orders of magnitude in single-precision. There is a difference in the converged values of k_{eff} between the PyTorch solvers and MERLIN of around 20 pcm. Arguably, this difference is small when viewed in the context of a fast-running whole-core calculation, and for an entirely different solver. The difference in the number of outer iterations between the PyTorch solver and MERLIN is stark, but justified by the remarks about frequency of scatter source resolution and the amount of work put into each outer iteration in Section 3.2. There is a negligible difference in the k_{eff} between the two floating point models of the PyTorch solver, but further investigation into the robustness of single-precision flux solves on real-life problems should be undertaken. The small difference in inner and outer iterations between the floating point models is likely explained by the presence of numerical artefacts. The number of inner iterations for the multigrid solvers are given as the sum of all smoothing iterations.

4. CONCLUSIONS

We have made a series of developments to a solver that was prototyped in our previous work [3]. These developments have made it more applicable to real-world use cases and have made it more performant and robust. The performance of the solver was showcased on a problem which we perceive to be notably more challenging than the previous one. We have shown that, when they are accelerated by a GPU, our methods can achieve pin-by-pin solve times arguably approaching those of a nodal diffusion smeared fuel-assembly solve (albeit requiring much more expensive hardware). It is crucial to note that our solver is implemented entirely in Python and requires close to zero knowledge of specialist GPU programming paradigms, toolkits or APIs, such as CUDA, which highlights the significant implementation advantages and development efficiencies attributed to the NN4PDEs methodology.

Further work should explore applications in more than two energy groups, particularly since resolving upscatter will become important. Trained AI avenues should be explored, as it is anticipated that linking a PyTorch-based solver to a PyTorch-based AI model should be straightforward. Incorporating the solver within data assimilation or uncertainty quantification workflows could also be investigated, thanks to the backpropagation algorithm inherent to PyTorch. Different discretisations should be looked at, such as the ConvFEM [2], which may make better use of the sparsity in its corresponding tensor of kernels, such as the one shown in (5). While extension of the solver to non-uniform grids may not appear to have associated with it any huge performance penalty, which is briefly discussed in Section 2.4, this should be more precisely analysed by comparing both versions of the solver on differently-sized uniformly-spaced test cases. Finally, future comparisons to parallelised CPU codes written in compiled languages would be valuable to quantify the tradeoff between the rapid development enabled by high-level abstractions in PyTorch and the absolute performance of more traditional solvers.

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